

Supplementary Data

Measurement of sENG via ELISA

Mouse sENG levels in plasma

Figure S1: sENG levels in independent control and CDAA-HFD groups without monoclonal antibody treatment. Data are presented as median with interquartile range. Mann-Whitney test, ** $p < 0.01$; 6 animals per group.

Human sENG levels in media

Figure S2: sENG levels in independent control and ox-LDL induced groups without monoclonal antibody treatment.. Data are presented as median with interquartile range. Mann-Whitney test, * $p < 0.05$; $n = 5$, showing representative figures from 3 independent experiments.

Supplementary Data

Figure S3: Mouse sENG

Gel 1

Gel 2

Supplementary Data

Figure S4: Human sENG

Gel 1

Gel 2

Supplementary Data

Figure S5: Confirmation of secondary antibody specificity by omission of primary antibody (mouse ENG)

Gel 1

Gel 2

Supplementary Data

Figure S6: Confirmation of secondary antibody specificity by omission of primary antibody (human ENG)

Gel 1

Gel 2

Supplementary Data

Figure S7: Ponceau S staining of mouse plasma samples

Control █
CDAA-HFD █
CDAA-HFD+M1043 █

Gel 1

Gel 2

Supplementary Data

Figure S8: Ponceau S staining of human culture media samples

Gel 1

Control █
ox-LDL █
ox-LDL+TRC105 █

Gel 2

